

The Psychological Well-Being of Breadwinners in Selected Families of a Third-Class Municipality: A Literature Review

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Abstract:- This literature focuses on understanding the psychological well-being of breadwinners from families. This is the basis of the action that can benefit society in connection to mental health for the community. This literature includes relevant research and literature from both local and international sources and is referenced with various recommendations, ideas, suggestions, ideas, concepts, and generalizations. The researchers of this study have worked their utmost effort to learn about and examine the studies pertaining to the subject under examination that has been published by various researchers and academics.

I. INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization's (WHO, 2017) Sustainable Development Goals highlighted the importance of and priority to adolescent mental well-being. The economic crisis brought on by the Covid-19 outbreak has undeniably had a substantial impact on the mental health and general well-being of Filipinos. According to Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA) – wherein cites in the Family Income Expenditure Survey that 18.1 percentage of Filipinos whose fundamental food and non-food needs cannot be satisfactorily met by their individual per capita income. According to PSA, the Covid-19 epidemic from 2020 was one of the main causes of the rapidly rising number of Filipinos who live below the poverty line, which amounts to about 1 in 5 of them. The difficulties of daily existence must be overcome by families in lower socioeconomic classes. Poor children frequently have to sacrifice their education in order to support their family, despite the irony that education is most likely the only way for them to escape poverty. Poverty has negative effects on all stages of life, as well as on the psychological aspects of health. Poverty is a significant socioeconomic factor contributing to health disparities (Ho et al., 2022). The abrupt changes in the social and cultural spheres will inevitably impact the educational systems of the various nations at this juncture (Ngoho and Tinapay, 2022). Education provides an individual with the required information and skills to act as a contributing member of society (Colina and Tinapay, 2023).

II. LITERATURE DISCUSSION

A. Psychological Well-being

General functioning and emotional stability are referred to as a person's "psychological well-being" in this context. It is the combination of health and performance. It is essential to be able to experience unpleasant or painful emotions; constant pleasure is not necessary for health. The ability to control these unpleasant or agonizing emotions is crucial for long-term health. Psychological well-being can also refer to an individual's general functioning and emotional stability. It combines favorable emotions with effective performance. Stability enables an individual or population to develop and prosper (Ruggeri et al., 2020).

Well-being is a dynamic concept that incorporates health-related activities as well as behavioral, social, and psychological aspects. Well-being and positive mental health are synonymous. According to the World Health Organization, positive mental health is "a state of well-being in which the individual realizes his or her own abilities, can deal with the typical stresses of life, can work effectively and fruitfully, and can contribute to his or her community". This definition of well-being, which extends beyond the absence of mental illness, includes the concept that life is pleasant.

The concept of wellbeing is conceptualized in numerous forms across disciplines. The majority of psychologists believe that high levels of psychological functioning and positive life events are indicators of happiness. The involvement and support of a parent is increasingly fundamental to the educational success of a child (CN Grageda, et.al, 2022). Ryff took this into account and developed a model of psychological well-being that incorporates six distinct aspects of positive functioning: autonomy, environmental mastery, personal development, life purpose, positive relationships with others, and self-acceptance. Examples of autonomy include independence and self-determination, the capacity to resist social pressure to think and act in particular ways, the capacity to regulate one's own behavior, and the capacity to evaluate oneself according to personal standards. Environmental mastery refers to a sense of control and competence in one's surroundings, the ability to manage a variety of outside activities and seize opportunities, and the capacity to select or create contexts that satisfy one's demand and ideals.

Personal growth is the state of self-realization and the feeling that one is getting better and better as time goes on. It is a change that shows more self-awareness and effectiveness of growth and development that never stops. Having a purpose in life means that you have goals and a sense of direction, believe that your present and past lives have worth, and have beliefs that give your life a purpose as well as goals and objectives for living. Positive connections with other people are described as being cozy, satisfying, and trustworthy, as well as caring about the well-being of others, being good at empathy, affection, and closeness, and understanding that relationships are based on giving and receiving. Last but not least, self-acceptance, which Celestine (2017) defines as having a positive view of oneself, accepting one's good and bad traits, and having had positive feelings about oneself in the past. This model was made after a lot of research was done on how people act. The most common form of the Psychological Wellbeing Scales has 42 items, half of which are written in a positive way and half of which are written in a negative way (Gao and McLellan, 2018).

The psychological well-being of rural students is higher than that of urban students, according to a study called "Psychological Well-being of Adolescents in Relation to School Environment and Place of Living." This study was published in the International Journal of Movement Education and Social Sciences. Alves and Rodrigues (2010) also found a link between living in a big city and the chance of having emotional problems. They point out that, despite its rural roots, it is still thought of as a nice and healthy place to live, where relationships are better and last longer, which helps people feel more emotionally stable and improves their well-being. In the city, on the other hand, ties are often unstable, which makes bonds about a wide range of topics more unstable. These factors, along with higher rates of stress and violence, for example, contribute to residents' perceptions of life in the urban environment as being less pleasant than that of residents in rural areas, especially for those who live in the area's periphery that is marked by misery. Family and community ties, which are more common in rural regions, are essential for coping with the unpleasant occurrences that are specific to poverty, and when they are upheld, they typically improve wellbeing and mental health (Persaud, 2018). In response to the COVID-19 pandemic, a foreign study says that many countries have put limits on daily (work) life. The World Health Organization (2020) says that the COVID-19 pandemic, which has killed millions of people, is a global health emergency. In order to keep health care systems from being overworked, governments used lock-downs, closing schools and businesses, and social distance rules to slow the spread of epidemics until vaccines or treatments were available (Gomez et al., 2020).

These rules have a big effect on how people work every day, the economy (like unemployment; see Crawford et al., 2020), and the places where people work. Due to company and school closings, many people who didn't lose their jobs are now forced to work from home, where they have to balance the many needs of work and family, especially if they have kids. Based on occupational health theories, it was thought that factors like the length of the pandemic, its demands (like the need to work from home or the closing of

child care facilities), and personal and work-related resources (like social support from coworkers, job autonomy, partner support, and corona self-efficacy) all had an effect on employee exhaustion. Researchers can help improve occupational health by learning more about the needs and resources of different jobs.

Indicating that the COVID-19 pandemic has a much greater negative control on women's mental health than it does on men. Future studies should look at whether this is because of the pandemic's reinforcement of established gender stereotypes or for other causes. To create treatments that lessen the psychological effects of the epidemic, governments and policymakers must focus exclusively on women. Conceptual starting points for such interventions can include expanding childcare services, granting workers more freedom at work, and adopting equitable methods of allocating home chores so that partners of working women can provide them with more support (Meyer et al., 2021). Local studies are also done to find out how the employees' mental health is and if it changes depending on the type of employee. In this study, researchers looked for signs of psychological health. Some of the things they found were company confidence, leadership, communication, policy, business continuity, job enablement, fairness, and support. Psychological well-being measures are used to figure out how resilient employees are in relation to the COVID-19 outbreak. The signs show how the PERMA theory works. Positive emotions show that the workers are happy and content, and that they have faith in the company. Role enablement shows how much workers care about their jobs and the company. They are very interested in and focused on what they are doing. Relationships are the best way to tell if someone is happy, and they can be judged on how well they lead, communicate, treat others, and support them. There is a reason for the steps that were created to aid the students throughout the pandemic. The Philippine State University's ability to continue operating despite the epidemic demonstrates how well it was able to adjust to the circumstances. With the results given, individuals exhibit great well-being in fairness because they feel their coworkers treated them properly during the pandemic.

They also believed that during the pandemic, the University of Southeastern Philippines has treated individuals from all backgrounds fairly. Comparatively to teaching and non-teaching staff, administrators exhibit higher levels of confidence inside the organization, as well as in terms of leadership, communication, policies, and role facilitation. Administrators demonstrate their confidence and ability to lead in the face of the pandemic. Contrarily, non-teaching staff exhibit great well-being in terms of business continuity. They believe that despite the pandemic, they are capable of executing their job and can adjust to flexible work arrangements (Arbiol et al., 2021).

Also, the well-being of Filipino orphans was the focus of a local study by Angelo Carlo D. Pilapil (2017) because people who go through major life changes and persistent issues, including losing one or both of their parents, are affected for the rest of their lives. The study sought to find out how happy and psychologically healthy these individuals

were because orphans are more likely to experience negative outcomes that compromise their ability to fulfill their personal goals for happiness and self-satisfaction (Pilapil, 2015). They still considered themselves to be generally happy despite being apart from their family, which is the most important aspect of a person's existence. When given the chance to prove themselves, they had shown that being orphans did not make them weak people; on the contrary, it made them stronger. They were able to achieve what life had been keeping from people - one's joy and fulfillment in life – thanks to their courage, innate goodness, sound judgment, strong faith, being realistic, and protecting the environment.

B. Breadwinners

The COVID-19 epidemic caused economic chaos and instability, endangering family members' health and well-being over the country. The current circumstance makes it more difficult for breadwinners, who already face many challenges (Casipong et al., 2022). They are vulnerable to mental illnesses like stress, sadness, anxiety, substance addiction, and the recurrence of past mental illnesses, especially if they are the breadwinners. The major or lone revenue earner in a home is referred to informally as the "breadwinner." They generate the majority of the household income, and breadwinners frequently shoulder the bulk of the costs of maintaining the home and providing for their dependents. They are the household member who earns the majority of the income and is responsible for providing for the family's financial needs. To keep their family from going hungry, they give them meal tickets. Men, women, or both may be the primary wage earners (Treves-Kagan, 2022). Despite their many triumphs, breadwinners manage to keep healthy ties with their family and friends. Despite carrying a lot of weight, they continue to smile and put up a good front despite setbacks and rejection. They may experience issues that they were unable to handle without their mental health getting worse. They are the one who provides for the families' needs and puts the responsibility on their sleeves; it may be a man or woman. Their struggles to pay for household needs, the stress and setbacks brought on by their workload at work and at home, as well as the conflicts and setbacks with their spouse and kids that could have an impact on their psychological well-being (Taruc, 2019).

A few studies have looked at the role of the worker in society. A foreign study by Rachel Y. Guo (2019) found that becoming a father is a big step in life that comes with new chores and responsibilities as an adult. People said that the Chinese migrant workers had a strong sense of responsibility and that their families were important to them. Male workers, for example, "live through their children" and find meaning in their work by giving up things for them and working to improve their children's chances. Also, they don't always see themselves as people who take care of other people. Instead, they say they want to spend more time with their families. Men who are married tend to be more careful at work because they can't afford to take chances with their income.

However, male employees may organize a resistance movement and fight for improved working conditions. As a result, a more complex framework is offered for comprehending how work and family relationships function

in the lives of working-class men, one that is connected to but extends beyond the role of the male breadwinner. Instead of supporting the stereotype of emotionally aloof working-class fathers and husbands, the study broadens our understanding of what it means to be a man by looking at how men feel about their families. They were emotionally stable because of them being the male and husband of the family. It also incorporates their culture that they must provide to their family because it is what they believe.

It is also supported that in this foreign study, family has always been the focus of breadwinning; to support their family, people take on additional jobs and work a variety of extracurricular activities. The majority of breadwinners believe that it is essential for people to be a part of a community and social network that accepts and loves them for who they are as individuals. The fact that they feel welcomed, liked, and have listeners is the major indicator that they experience adequate social support. The breadwinners nevertheless hold on to the belief that their families play a significant role in their social support in light of the examination of the support that is accessible. The findings of this study are consistent with those of Diaz and Bui's (2017) study, which found that one of the most important elements affecting a person's happiness in their current situation was their perceptions of social support from their family. Breadwinners are struggling to survive this pandemic. Even though their health is at stake, they continue to put in a lot of effort to support their families and themselves during these trying times, dual employment and side businesses. The findings demonstrated that despite these circumstances and the burden of family responsibilities, breadwinners are eager to carry on living their lives and achieving their ambitions. By evaluating their lifestyles with satisfaction, the breadwinners' sense of contentment demonstrates that they had a high level of well-being, which raised their judgment of it.

A foreign study also by Aimzhan Iztayeva (2021), custodial single fathers who work full-time who are the breadwinners are in a unique position to challenge conventional gender roles. Both providing care and earning a living have gendered cultural meanings. Regardless of whether a person is a caregiver, paternity is linked to earning a living, which limits care giving because men are typically seen as the "ideal worker" standard, who has little free time for family obligations. There is frequently a "fatherhood bonus" in pay as a result of this connection. That is, fathers who are married, hold advanced degrees, and interact with their children according to gender norms. Wives are regarded as dependable, diligent employees who need a living wage to support their families. The conflict between a "providing" father and a "nurturing" father is exacerbated by the expectations that each role entails: the provider role demands a larger commitment to the career, while the nurturing father role anticipates spending more time with the kids.

It appears that dads who follow the "new fatherhood ideal" increase the amount of time they spend with their kids in order to reconcile this contradiction, but they do so by restricting or including them in their free time rather than by cutting back on their working hours. Fathers want to be with

their kids more, but "their attempts eventually run across institutional resistances that put men's egalitarian goals out of reach". According to this study, unmarried men with children were neither "ideal employees" and put their family and caring obligations first. However, employers still pressed for unrestricted availability. Custodial single fathers with advanced degrees said they had an easier time getting additional flexibility at their current jobs. Some of them could have changed to a job or work path that gave them this freedom. In low-skill or blue-collar jobs, men had to deal with more restrictions. Their plans were not always in their hands, and their unwavering commitment to child care often caused problems and misunderstandings at work. This has shown how sensitive custodial single fathers, especially those who work for low wages, were to the COVID-19 problem. The conflict between work and family that they were dealing with got a lot worse, which hurt their physical and mental health. Even though these guys were able to get through the problems caused by being a single parent and the epidemic, the study's results have important implications for policy and practice. Both other parents and single dads may have problems from time to time.

According to a local study, social interactions and activities have been recognized as essential factors supporting human health and wellbeing throughout the lifetime. People are social creatures that depend on one another. For most people, it is gratifying to feel valued, bolstered, or appreciated. Family and friends, as well as other social relationships, are important in one's life because they can affect motivation and a sense of belonging. Perceived social support and subjective well-being are thought to be relevant to the setting of the bread because they could give more up-to-date information about the ideas. Most people find it satisfying when they are made to feel important, strong, or admired. A person's life is essential because of the influence that family, friends, and other social connections can have on motivation and a feeling of identity. People think that perceived social support and emotional well-being are important to the setting of the breadwinners because they could give more up-to-date information about the winners of the idea (Javier et al., 2018). We then searched for appropriate respondents who could provide guidance and contribute to the growing body of research by describing how respondents view the social support they receive from those around them, even though the researchers are aware that research on subjective well-being has expanded significantly over many years. Gender identities are commonly the focus of studies on breadwinners; male or female breadwinners have been compared to or appraised, and the decline of male breadwinners has also been studied.

According to the study's findings, breadwinners have an extremely strong sense of the availability and sufficiency of social assistance. They can nevertheless appreciate the readily available and adequate help, especially from their families, friends, and coworkers, despite the difficulties of being the major provider. Their family was perceived as needing the most help, probably because they are able to address their requirements and are the closest social connection. It is evident that a person's family has a significant influence on their life and how they behave when

they are aware that their family accepts and loves them for who they are. Based on research findings that examined breadwinners' perceptions of social support and their subjective wellbeing, the researchers published *Keep in Touch (KIT): Maintaining Quality Social Relationships for a Better Well Being*. KIT is a program designed to help breadwinners improve and maintain their sense of happiness, life satisfaction, and perceived social support from supportive connections. This can be advantageous, especially when assuming more demanding tasks and obligations as the primary provider for the family (Casipong, 2022). This backed with a local study that had been conducted earlier that identified social contacts and activities as critical components of promoting long-term health and wellbeing in humans. People are social creatures that depend on one another. Most people find it satisfying when they are made to feel important, strong, or admired. A person's life is essential because of the influence that family, friends, and other social connections can have on motivation and a feeling of identity.

This support has an immediate effect on our health and happiness because it gives us a feeling of security, routine, belonging, and purpose (Bahji et al., 2020). Perceived social support and subjective well-being are important to the context of the study's respondents, who are breadwinners, because they may offer new views on the concepts. Studies on breadwinners often talk about gender identities. Both male and female breadwinners have been compared to or judged against each other, and the fall of male breadwinners has also been studied. When experts look at studies and books, they don't understand them very well. In light of what we've already talked about, the main goal of our study was to find out how the breadwinners felt about their social support in terms of how many supportive ties they thought they had and how many they thought they had. We also wanted to find out how they felt about their own well-being in terms of life satisfaction, positive effects, and negative effects.

According to these results, breadwinners place a high value on social assistance in terms of both its availability and sufficiency. Despite the difficulties that come with being the primary provider, they are nevertheless able to notice the readily available and adequate help, particularly from their family, friends, and coworkers. Most of the help was perceived to be coming from their family, probably because they can take care of their needs and are their closest social ties. The fact that they are aware of their family's affection and acceptance of them for who they are and how they have helped them through difficult times suggests that their family is significant in their lives and influences how they respond. They appear to love and work hard for their family, based on their extremely high positive influence (Diener et al., 2018).

III. CONCLUSION

The epidemic caused by COVID-19 has had an impact on workers' psychological well-being all around the world. During the worst of the Saudi Arabian lockdown, most of the professors and staff at King Saudi University said they had anxiety, sadness, and trouble sleeping (Alfawaz, Wani, Aljumah, et al., 2020). Hamouche (2020) says that COVID-19 is bad for the mental health of workers because it adds

stressors like the perception of safety, the threat and risk of contagion, the inability to lose weight in the face of unknown circumstances, confinement and quarantine, stigma and social exclusion, financial loss, and the uncertainty of a job. The ongoing COVID-19 pandemic has had a negative effect on every part of the Philippine economy. According to the most recent Labor Force Survey (LFS) from the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA), there are currently 3.5 million unemployed Filipinos and the unemployment rate is 7.4%. Because they bargain together to improve their financial circumstances, unions are affected by these negative effects (Bitonio, 2020). A breadwinner and their psychological well-being give a big impact on an individual. The economic standing of these breadwinners living being the sole income earner has been recognized by different organizations from the foreign and local sources such as PIDS, WHO, UN, ASA and many more. Regardless of their employment status, temporary agency workers enjoy excellent job satisfaction, according to a Chambel et al. (2016) study. However, the type of job contract makes a difference in a person's level of well-being (Kauhanen & Natti, 2015).

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